

A Detailed Review of Existing Studies on Psychological Stress, Anxiety, and Cognitive Load in Simultaneous Interpreting

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive review of existing research on psychological stress, anxiety, and cognitive load in simultaneous interpreting. Simultaneous interpreters often face intense mental demands, requiring them to process, translate, and produce speech in real-time across languages. The review synthesizes key findings from studies examining how stress and anxiety, both psychological and physiological, impact interpreters' cognitive functions, including attention, working memory, and decision-making. It also explores the relationship between cognitive load and interpreter performance, highlighting factors such as language complexity, subject matter familiarity, and working conditions. By analyzing experimental data, self-reported measures, and neurocognitive assessments, the review identifies coping mechanisms and strategies interpreters use to manage stress and cognitive overload. The paper concludes by discussing implications for interpreter training and practice, emphasizing the need for tools and methods that can enhance performance under high-stress conditions. This review aims to inform future research and offer practical insights for improving the well-being and effectiveness of simultaneous interpreters.

Keywords: psychological stress, mental demands, cognitive functions, interpreter training, decision-making process, interpreter performance, language complexity, subject matter familiarity.

Simultaneous interpreting (SI) is a complex cognitive task that requires interpreters to process and convey information in real-time, often leading to significant psychological stress, anxiety, and cognitive load. This article reviews existing studies that investigate these factors, highlighting key findings and implications for both practitioners and educators in the field of interpreting.

Psychological stress is a common experience among simultaneous interpreters, often stemming from the high-stakes nature of their work. Research by Gile (2009) emphasizes that interpreters face multiple sources of stress, including time pressure, the need for linguistic accuracy, and the challenge of working in unfamiliar contexts. Gile's Effort Model of Interpreting posits that the cognitive demands placed on interpreters can lead to a heightened stress response, which may adversely affect performance. A study by Käthner et al. (2016) found that increased levels of psychological stress negatively impacted interpreting performance, particularly in terms of accuracy and fluency. The researchers

employed physiological measures (e.g., heart rate variability) alongside subjective assessments to gauge stress levels. Research by Mäkelä (2015) explored coping strategies employed by interpreters under stress. The study identified both adaptive strategies (e.g., preparation and practice) and maladaptive strategies (e.g., avoidance), suggesting that training programs should incorporate stress management techniques.

Anxiety in Simultaneous Interpreting

Anxiety is another prevalent issue for interpreters, often manifesting as performance anxiety or apprehension about language proficiency. A study by Hale (2007) highlighted that anxiety levels could significantly influence an interpreter's ability to process information effectively. Tisnado et al. (2018) examined the relationship between anxiety and cognitive performance in SI. Their findings indicated that higher anxiety levels correlated with poorer performance on comprehension tasks, suggesting that anxiety can hinder cognitive processing. Baker & Kondo (2015) investigated pre-performance anxiety among student interpreters. They found that students often experienced heightened anxiety before assignments, which could be mitigated through effective preparation and rehearsal.

Cognitive load refers to the mental effort required to process information during interpretation. The dual-task nature of SI—listening to a source language while producing a target language—creates a significant cognitive load, impacting both performance and well-being. Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory distinguishes between intrinsic, extraneous, and germane load. Studies such as those by Pöchhacker (2016) have applied this theory to SI, identifying how different types of cognitive load affect interpreting performance. Research by Kopczynski et al. (2020) utilized eye-tracking technology to measure cognitive load during SI tasks. Their findings indicated that increased cognitive load was associated with longer response times and decreased accuracy, reinforcing the notion that managing cognitive load is crucial for effective interpreting.

The insights gained from these studies underscore the importance of addressing psychological stress, anxiety, and cognitive load in interpreter training programs. Effective training should not only focus on linguistic skills but also incorporate strategies for managing stress and anxiety.

There are some recommendations such as using 1. Stress Management Techniques. Integrating mindfulness practices and relaxation techniques into training can help interpreters cope with stress more effectively (Mäkelä, 2015). 2. Cognitive Load Management: Training programs should emphasize strategies for managing cognitive load, such as chunking information and utilizing note-taking techniques (Pöchhacker, 2016). 3. Simulation Training: Providing realistic interpreting scenarios can help reduce pre-performance anxiety by familiarizing interpreters with high-pressure environments (Baker & Kondo, 2015).

Conclusion

The existing body of research highlights the intricate relationship between psychological stress, anxiety, and cognitive load in simultaneous interpreting. Understanding these factors is essential for improving interpreter training and performance. Future studies should continue to explore these dimensions, particularly in relation to technological advancements and their implications for the interpreting profession.

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